

NESTORE

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D1.4 NESTORE Communication Toolkit

MEANS TO COMMUNICATE THE PROJECT

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Approvals

DATE	NAME	ORGANIZATION	ROLE
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Short Abstract

This document describes the different tools available to the project partners and press contacts to ensure the wide and professional dissemination of the project.

Key Words

Website, Flyer, Press Release, Templates

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1. Introduction and background

This communication toolkit is the necessary material to the implementation of the first dissemination phase described in D1.3 – Dissemination plan. This phase aims to prepare the dissemination and communication activities as well as the set up of an initial communication toolkit. D1.3 gives an extensive presentation of the different dissemination tools; thus this deliverable only gives a snapshot of what is available so far and what are the next iterative steps for the development of the toolkit.

2. Concept

The NESTORE communication toolkit aims to help informing the general public, build a network of relevant stakeholders and foster penetration of NESTORE in the relevant sectors. It aims to provide partners and press contacts with the necessary tools to ensure the wide and professional dissemination of the project.

3. Accessibility and inclusiveness

Similarly to the project website, careful considerations have been given to gender-sensitive aspects of the different communication tools. Documents are written in a level of language adequate to the audience it aims to reach and translations will be provided by partners as they disseminate the materials in their respective country. The communication toolkit will finally be enriched with new images in the near future following the needs and requests from partners and press contacts; these images will however ensure a wide coverage of all potential users of the NESTORE system.

4. Composition

The NESTORE communication toolkit is composed of:

- The two versions of the project logo (horizontal and vertical);
- The generic version of the project flyer (web and print formats);
- The project templates (PPT and DOC formats);
- A first press release entitled: “Launch of the NESTORE Project on Novel Empowering Solutions and Technologies for Older people to Retain Everyday life activities”;
- A collection of images including both photos of the consortium and graphical pictures used on the website to illustrate the technological aspects of the project.

5. Management

The toolkit will be regularly updated and fed with new communication assets as the project moves forward. It will be composed of more content-related materials (especially regarding images) and will offer evidence-based resources such as briefs and press releases informing about major achievements and milestones reached by the NESTORE project.

